

Microstructure and compression behavior of Ag–W metal matrix composite produced from core-shell powder by spark plasma sintering: case study

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Abstract:

Metal matrix composites represent an interesting class of materials with an exclusive combination of properties. In this study, Ag–W metal matrix composite was produced from W@Ag core-shell powders using a spark plasma sintering technique. The microstructure of the default powder and as-produced composite investigated by scanning electron microscopy confirmed that the composite is formed by Ag matrix with spherical W particulates. Observation of the microstructure of the composite material deformed by tension and compression revealed that the interface between the matrix and the reinforced particulates is the weakest link of its structure.

Keywords: Core-shell powder; Silver; Tungsten; Spark plasma sintering; Metal matrix composite, Compression deformation.

1. Introduction

Metal matrix composites (MMCs) represent a class of highly sophisticated materials with a unique combination of properties including e.g., enhanced strength, wear resistance, and reduced thermal expansion [1], that are well-suited for a diverse array of applications such as aerospace, military, sports, and electronics [2, 3]. MMCs include a continuous metallic matrix and a meticulously selected reinforcement, which is deliberately chosen based on its specific properties and the desired features of the composite material [2, 4]. It is known that the shape of reinforcement (fibers, particles) affects the structure and properties of composite materials [5].

One of the MMCs used in electronics as electrical contacts is a combination of two immiscible metals such as silver and tungsten [6]. Such composites, which can also have

antibacterial potential, have usually been formed by spherical particulates in a soft matrix and are usually produced by hot pressing Ag and W powders [6, 7].

A trendy branch of MMC preparation represents the methods of powder metallurgy (PM) such as hot extrusion, and hot pressing [8]. Besides them, spark plasma sintering (SPS) is a promising method in this respect, if small parts should be prepared. Compared to other PM methods, SPS allows the preservation of fine microstructure [9] due to the short-term nature of the process usually combining only a few minutes of sintering and consolidation into a single operation step [8, 10]. A wide range of materials can be produced by SPS technique [11, 12], for example, high-entropy alloys [9], composites with extremely high strength [13], and intermetallics [14].

Recently, core-shell powders became a popular material used for MMCs production [15-19]. A combination of the SPS technique with the usage of core-shell powders enables the production of metastable metal matrix composites (m-MMCs) thanks to the sintering of the shell surfaces and suppression of the diffusion processes between the core and shell [20]. Recently we studied the structure and plastic deformation of Ag–Cu m-MMCs prepared from Cu@Ag core-shell powders where the core and shell materials show very similar mechanical properties [20]. Only a few attempts to produce micro-sized MMCs from Ag@(W/WO₃) core-shell powders [15, 21-23] have been performed to study their mechanical and electric properties [24-26].

In the present work, we describe the microstructure and mechanical behavior of a model MMC combining a very soft Ag matrix (300 – 700 MPa [27]) reinforced with high-strength W particulates (1200 – 4000 MPa [27]) prepared from W@Ag core-shell powder using the SPS technique. Compared to the mentioned Ag–Cu system, Ag–W MMC reported here exhibits entirely different compression behavior, not only in terms of mechanical properties but also due to their complete immiscibility.

2. Experimental

The W@Ag core-shell powder with a volume ratio of W and Ag 50:50 was manufactured in SAFINA a.s. The production of the powder consists of two steps: i) gas atomization of W powder; ii) dosage of AgNO₃ in an alkaline solution for obtaining pure Ag for precipitation of Ag on W particulates. The powder particle distribution was measured by laser diffraction on the Malvern Panalytical Mastersizer 3000 machine.

The core-shell powder was compacted by SPS technology using FCT Systeme HP-D 10 device to produce a rounded sample with 20 mm in diameter and 6 mm in height. For each sample, 30 g of powder was used. The parameters of the compaction process were identical to those described in detail for the production of Cu–Ag m-MMCs in the work [20], i.e., i) force of 25 kN (corresponds to a pressure of 80 MPa); ii) heating rate of $100\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C min}^{-1}$; iii) compaction temperature of $700\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$; iv) dwell time of 5 min; v) cooling segment – turning off the heating to achieve the maximal cooling rate of the device. The time dependencies of the recorded height reduction, step temperature, current flow, and applied force during the process are shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 Recorded height reduction (blue) applied force (black), current flow (grey), and sample temperature (red) during the SPS process.

A morphology of the default W@Ag core-shell powder as well as its microstructure and the microstructure of the Ag–W MMC were characterized using scanning electron microscopy (SEM Tescan Mira) equipped by energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS). The detailed microstructural characterization of the as-produced Ag–W MMC was performed on the $50 \times 80\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ area with a step size of $0.1\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ using SEM (FEI Quanta 3D FEG) including electron backscatter diffraction (EBSD). The obtained EBSD data were processed using TSL OIM8 software (v. 8.0). All the microstructures were observed on the ground and polished surfaces.

Tensile and compression tests were performed to investigate the mechanical properties of the obtained Ag–W MMC. In both cases, Instron 5882 machine with a deformation rate of 10^{-3} s^{-1} at ambient temperature was used. Tensile tests were performed on samples with a “dog-bone” shape with dimensions of 7.0 mm length, 2.0 mm width and 0.55 mm thickness. Cuboid samples with a 6.0 mm height and square base of $4 \times 4\text{ mm}$ were used for compression tests. Samples for tensile

and compression tests were prepared by electro-erosive cutting from the samples produced by SPS. The cross-sections of the deformed materials were observed using SEM Tescan Mira.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Characterization of the starting material

The distribution of particle size in the W@Ag core-shell powder is shown in Fig. 2. The particle sizes exhibit a typical Gaussian distribution with dimensions ranging from 20 to 80 μm with a median value of 37.1 μm , which is approximately 10 μm larger than the size of Cu@Ag core-shell described in [20].

Fig. 2 Size distribution and cumulative curve of the W@Ag core-shell powder.

The morphology of the W@Ag core-shell powder is characterized by a spherical/rounded shape with the surface looking like the orange peel texture (Fig. 3). There can also be seen voids on the surface of some particles (Fig. 3a, yellow arrows). The presence of these defects (as well as the surface roughness described in the study [20]) can affect the microstructure of the composite produced by the SPS process. If the void is too deep and reaches the W core, islands of sintered W can be observed within the microstructure of the produced composite.

The microstructure and the chemical composition of the W@Ag core-shell powder cross-section are shown in Fig. 4. Unfortunately, a height difference between the hard W core and the very ductile Ag shell occurred during the metallographic preparation of the sample due to a different response of Ag and W to the grinding and subsequential polishing. In addition, wide hollow pores are visible between the two component materials, an example of which is marked by a red arrow in Fig. 4. The origin of this defect is unclear, it could occur either during the metallographic preparation or the manufacturing method during the Ag deposition onto the W

core. In this case, it could result from the 25 % difference in lattice parameters of fcc Ag ($a = 0.4086 \text{ nm}$ [28, 29]) and bcc W ($a = 0.3155 \text{ nm}$ [30, 31]).

Fig. 3 SEM micrographs of the W@Ag core-shell powder morphology. Yellow arrows in (a) mark the voids in the shell of the particles.

Fig. 4 SEM micrograph and EDS elements distribution maps of W and Ag at the cross-section of the W@Ag core-shell powder. A red arrow shows the area of bad adhesion between the shell and core.

3.2. Characterization of the Ag–W MMC

The microstructure of the Ag–W MMC is shown in Fig. 5. It is seen that the SPS process made it possible to produce the MMC characterized by Ag matrix and W particulates. However, a lot of W clusters are observed here. As was mentioned above, it can be a result of a defective surface of the core-shell powder particles (Fig. 3a, yellow arrows), which makes it possible to join the W core together during the SPS process. Figure 5 also shows a high number of voids in the MMC microstructure. It is apparent that the shape and size of the voids correspond to the size and shape of W particulates. These voids occurred because of dropping out of the W particulates during the grinding and polishing of the material. The dropping out of the W particulates is a consequence of the fact that the W and Ag do not show any solubility according to the phase diagram [32]. A weak bonding between Ag and W was also observed in [15], where the W–Ag composites were prepared with different Ag contents. As a result, it was impossible to characterize the porosity of the Ag–W MMC. We might expect that the true porosity of the compacted MMC will be on the same level as that determined for Ag–Cu MMCs, i.e. of the order of 10^{-2} – 10^{-1} %.

Fig. 5 SEM micrograph of the Ag–W MMC produced by SPS.

Figure 6 depicts the EBSD results of the Ag–W MMC produced by the SPS technique. Inverse pole figure (IPF) maps show a dual structure of the MMC – large W particulates consisting

of a few grains while being embedded in the Ag matrix with nanosized grains. The grain size analysis of both W and Ag (Fig. 7) documents that W grains have sizes in a range from a few μm up to almost 30 μm . Conversely, the majority of Ag grain sizes range between 500 nm and 1 μm . The difference in grain sizes of the two components of the MMC results from the production way of the core-shell powder – atomization of W particles and deposition of the Ag shell.

EDS element distribution maps (Fig. 6) show some fine particles of W in the Ag matrix. It is apparent that their distribution, size and shape are completely coincidental. Figure 5b shows the same type of pure elemental particles of W in the Ag matrix. Therefore, their occurrence can be attributed to the metallographic sample preparation when the hard but brittle W is broken and stuffed into a very soft and ductile Ag.

Fig. 6 IPF and EDS maps of the Ag–W MMC obtained from EBSD analysis.

Fig. 7 The plots of the grain sizes in the Ag–W m-MMC: a) W; b) Ag.

3.3. Mechanical testing

To investigate the mechanical properties of the Ag–W MMC produced by SPS technique, tensile and compression tests were aimed to be performed. Regrettably, it was impossible to obtain any reasonable result from tensile tests. Samples of a “dog-bone” shape tend to break apart during their insertion into the device clamp. For illustration, the fracture surface of such a damaged sample is shown in Figure 8. The fracture surface shows nondeformed W particulates. Moreover, when separated from the Ag matrix, these particulates left the dimples with corresponding shapes and sizes that are almost 100% smooth. It indicates that there was the weakest cohesion between the matrix and reinforcement particulates.

This finding can be related to the pulling out of the W particulates during grinding and polishing (Fig. 5). Figure 8 also shows that the area around the spherical particulates exhibits a fracture, characterized by dimples, confirming a ductile behavior of the Ag matrix. In fact, this fracture runs along the weakest path of the matrix among close particulates where the lowest force is necessary to separate the material. The EDS element distribution maps (Fig. 8) prove the presence of nondeformed W particulates in the ductile Ag matrix. Similar behavior of composite material

failure by a decohesion along the interface between the hard particulates (ZrO_2/SiO_2) and the soft matrix (Al) was described in the study [5]. In addition, the authors of [33] described three types of particulate defects at the fracture surface of 6082Al matrix composite reinforced with Mo particulates: (i) fractured particulates; (ii) pull-out particulates; (iii) pull-out particulates pits. In the present study, the fractured particulates were not observed, however, the (ii) and (iii) types are shown in Figure 8 and marked by blue and red arrows, respectively.

Fig. 8 SEM micrograph and EDS maps of the Ag–W m-MMC fracture surface after the “tensile” test. Blue arrows depict the W particulates, red arrows mark the holes after dropped W particulates.

The dependence of the true stress–true strain in compression of Ag–W MMC together with those of pure Ag as well as of recently studied Ag–Cu MMC [20], is shown in Fig. 9. As expected, the value of the compression yield stress (CYS) is higher than that of the pure matrix material – Ag. On the other hand, it is nearly the same as that of Ag–Cu MMC containing much softer reinforcing particulates.

The yield stress, σ_C , of a compressed composite can be written as [20, 34-37]

$$\sigma_C = \sigma_m + f(\Delta\sigma_D, \Delta\sigma_{LT}, \Delta\sigma_{GB}, \Delta\sigma_{Or}, \Delta\sigma_{SS}, \dots), \quad (1)$$

where σ_m is the CYS of the matrix, $\Delta\sigma_D$ is the stress of the dislocations, $\Delta\sigma_{TM}$ is a thermal mismatch, $\Delta\sigma_{GND}$ is the geometrical necessity, $\Delta\sigma_{LT}$ is the contribution of the load transfer, $\Delta\sigma_{GB}$ is the contribution of grain boundary (Hall-Petch) strengthening, $\Delta\sigma_{Or}$ is the contribution of the particle (Orowan) strengthening, and $\Delta\sigma_{SS}$ is the stress contribution from solid solution. The function in Eq. (1) is complex [38, 39], however, it can also be considered as a simple sum of the

components [34, 35, 40]. In the Ag–W MMCs, we can exclude the contribution of $\Delta\sigma_{SS}$ as Ag and W are immiscible.

Fig. 9 Compression true stress-true-strain curves of the Ag–W MMC. For comparison, the compression curves of pure Ag and Ag–Cu (45:55) MMC [20] are also shown.

The contribution $\Delta\sigma_D$ may be written as [41]

$$\Delta\sigma_D = AG|\mathbf{b}|\sqrt{\rho_{dis}}, \quad (2)$$

with the constant A , the shear modulus G , the Burgers vector \mathbf{b} , and the summary dislocation density ρ_{dis} . Accepting $A = 0.55$ [41], $G_{Ag} = 24.3$ GPa [42] and $|\mathbf{b}(\text{Ag})| = 0.290$ nm [43], and supposing the dislocation density in Ag to be $8 \times 10^{13} \text{ m}^{-2}$, i.e., similar to that measured in the Ag–Cu MMC)¹, the mean contribution of dislocations in the matrix to the stress is $\Delta\sigma_D = 35$ MPa.

The form of the term $\Delta\sigma_{LT}$ can be given as [44]

$$\Delta\sigma_{LT} = \frac{1}{2} \sigma_y \kappa f_v, \quad (3)$$

where κ is the aspect ratio of the reinforcements, σ_y is the yield stress of the particulate, and f_v is the volume fraction of the reinforcement phase. To estimate its contribution, we can use the values of $\kappa = 1$, $f_v = 0.50$, and $\sigma_y = 56$ MPa [20]. Then $\Delta\sigma_{LT} = 14$ MPa.

¹ Unpublished results

The contribution of the grain boundaries (Hall-Petch contribution) in polycrystalline materials with the grain size d_g causes an increase in the stress [45]

$$\Delta\sigma_{GB} = \frac{K_{GB}}{\sqrt{d_g}}, \quad (4)$$

with K_{GB} being constant. For Ag, we can use the values of $d_g = 0.75 \mu\text{m}$ and $K_{GB} = 2.51 \text{ MPa mm}^{1/2}$ [45]. Supposing that the active area of Ag is 50% in the MMC which is composed of 50 % of both Ag and W, we obtain the value of $\Delta\sigma_{GB} = 45 \text{ MPa}$.

Then the effect of the Orowan strengthening must not be considered here. The large non-deformable particulates serve in the MMC as large objections reducing the active area. This effect was considered in the Hall-Petch strengthening above.

Supposing a simple addition of individual contributions, the summary increase of σ_m in the composite is then of about 94 MPa. This estimated value is close to the difference between measured values of CYS of the Ag–W MMC (135 MPa) and of the Ag matrix (35 MPa) [20], i.e. 100 MPa.

The fact that the values of CYS of Ag–W and Ag–Cu MMCs are very similar (Fig. 9) results from the fact that plastic deformation starts when the dislocations become move in the Ag matrix and that the modifications of the values of CYS in both cases are dominated by the behavior of Ag matrix.

In contrast to pure Ag and Ag–Cu MMC exhibiting a similar course of the true stress – true strain curve, its course for Ag–W MMC is quantitatively different during compression (Fig. 9). This is caused by the fact that W particulates do not deform plastically thus limiting plastic deformation to a more limited volume than it is in the case of both pure Ag and Ag–Cu MMC. In the latter one, plastic deformation also occurs in the particulates which strongly contributes to an increase of the strengthening and suppresses the fracture of the material. In this respect, the W particulates represent an objection to the plastic deformation of the MMC. Supposing the value of Young's modulus of W to be 370 GPa [46], the elastic deformation at 210 MPa where the plastic deformation of the MMC is 15.4 % (Fig 9), is about 0.068 % only. This causes large internal stress at the Ag/W interface which result eventually in fracturing the MMC. Additionally, a rather flat course of the deformation curve can be related to a relatively large size of the reinforcing particulates [47].

To characterize the plasticity during the compression, we can evaluate the work hardening rate as the change of true stress, σ , with true strain, ε , under constant deformation rate, $\dot{\varepsilon}$, [48],

$$\Theta = \left(\frac{\partial \sigma}{\partial \varepsilon} \right)_{\dot{\varepsilon}}, \quad (5)$$

and the work hardening exponent n [48],

$$n = \left(\frac{\partial \ln \sigma}{\partial \ln \varepsilon} \right)_{\dot{\varepsilon}}. \quad (6)$$

The dependences of both parameters on the true strain are shown in Fig. 10. Due to the flat dependence of σ vs. ε discussed above, the work hardening rate is quickly decreasing to zero at the ultimate compression stress (UCS) and reaching negative values during the fracturing the sample along the Ag/W interfaces as well as in the Ag matrix (Fig. 10a). It contrasts with the behavior of pure Ag and Ag-Cu MMC characterized by a continuous increase of the stress with the strain (Fig. 9). This difference results from the fact that W particulates do not deform plastically while the Cu ones in Ag-Cu MMCs do, and in addition, Cu particulates in corresponding MMC as well as pure Ag contained large grains [20] which strengthen similarly as documented in Fig. 10a.

The work hardening exponent narrates about the mechanism of plastic deformation. The values of $n = 0.15$ – 0.18 found for the Ag-W MMC (Fig. 10b) indicate that the deformation is realized by the slip and climb of dislocations in fine-grained Ag. Similar mechanism of the deformation was reported for fine-grained Ti [49]. A similar value of $n = 0.21$ was also measured at the early stage of the deformation of Ag-Cu MMC referring about starting the dislocation motion in fine-grained Ag matrix. However, with increasing stress, deformation also occurs in coarse-grained Cu particulates which is reflected in an increased value of n ($n = 0.31$). As an increase of n is attributed to deformation twinning in Ti [49], we may deduce that twinning is also operating in the Cu particulates. In the case of Ag possessing the grain size of 0.5 μm , the twinning can easily occur already at the early stage of deformation and lead to the subsequent increase of n value from 0.28 to 0.53. In Ag-W MMC, twinning was suppressed due to small grain size and non-deformability of W particles, thus, insignificant increase of n was observed.

Fig. 10 Characteristics of plastic deformation of Ag–W MMC. (a) work hardening rate; (b) work hardening exponent. The dependences of pure Ag and of Ag–Cu MMC are shown for comparison.

The microstructure of the fracture surfaces of Ag–W MMC after compression deformation is shown in Fig. 11). It is apparent that the W particulates remain unchanged (in terms of size and shape) after compression tests, which confirms that W was deformed elastically only. The above-mentioned concentration of the stress at the Ag/W interfaces results in the occurrence of cracking there. Then the fracture continues in a ductile manner through the joining Ag matrix. There are two types of morphology of the fracture, the dimple character of simple fracture, and the shear in the Ag matrix caused by the hard particulates moving during compression (Fig. 11). Nevertheless, the deformability of the Ag–W MMC exhibiting more than 15 % is relatively very good.

Fig. 11 SEM micrographs of the fracture surface of the Ag–W MMC after compression tests

4. Conclusions

In this study, an Ag–W metal matrix composite (MMC) was successfully fabricated using spark plasma sintering (SPS) from W@Ag core-shell powder. As a result, a dual structure was produced characterized by an Ag matrix with the submicrometer grain size and by reinforcing W particulates with the grain size of up to 30 μm. The increase in compression yield stress of the MMC compared to that of pure Ag, is attributed to the strengthening effects of dislocation, thermal mismatch, geometrical necessity, load transfer, and grain boundaries (Hall-Petch). A low and nearly constant value of the work hardening exponent implies that plastic deformation occurs in the Ag–W MMC via dislocation motion in the matrix, while the particulates do not deform during compression. The interface between the matrix and reinforcement particulates, however, was identified as the weakest link in the MMC structure. It suggests that further research is needed to improve the strength of this interface.

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Author contributions

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Data availability

The data used in this manuscript are available in the Zenodo repository at the following link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14775989>.

Declaration of the Conflict of Interest The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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